

JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
(JSAES)

Journal homepage: <http://jsaes.org/index.php/jsaes/index>

PHYSIOLOGICAL CHANGES AT TWO DIFFERENT MATURITY STAGES IN BANANA FRUIT DURING STORAGE AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

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Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 20 Sep 2023 Accepted: 05 Nov 2023</p>	<p>Bananas exhibit limited longevity under tropical conditions, facing challenges such as accelerated softening, age-related blemishes, unpleasant aroma, and susceptibility to cold damage when stored below 13°C. To address these issues, our research focused on developing an eco-friendly, non-chemical approach to prolong the shelf-life of bananas post-harvest. We discovered that ripe bananas maintain a higher level of firmness compared to their unripe counterparts as they age. Additionally, the Total Soluble Solids (TSS) content was notably higher in mature bananas as opposed to immature ones. To achieve these findings, various methods were employed to examine the deterioration effects during the ripening process. These included assessments of physical attributes such as color alterations, and biochemical assays to measure the build-up of specific molecules like superoxide anions, hydrogen peroxide, and malondialdehyde byproducts. We also evaluated the accumulation of thiobarbituric reactive compounds and calculated ion leakage percentages as markers of cell damage. Our results indicate that non-chemical treatments can significantly extend the shelf-life of bananas while preserving their quality. These alternative methods are not only health-conscious but also environmentally friendly, making them the focus of global research endeavors. The study opens up avenues for potential eco-friendly post-harvest treatments that could revolutionize the way we store and consume this popular fruit, ultimately contributing to food security and sustainability. By exploring non-chemical strategies for post-harvest preservation, this research adds significant value to the ongoing worldwide efforts to find healthful and environmentally sustainable methods for prolonging the shelf-life of perishable goods like bananas.</p>
<p>Keywords Bananas, Fruit, Maturity stages, Physiological changes Room temperature</p> <p>Ullah et al., (2023). Physiological changes at two different maturity stages in banana fruit during storage at room temperature: <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 1(2), 34-42.</p> <p>https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p>	
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1. INTRODUCTION

Banana (*Musa sapientum* L.) stands as a crucial tropical fruit, boasting a worldwide annual yield of roughly 145.4 million metric tons. Asia alone contributes approximately 69 million tons to this global figure (FAO, 2011). This fruit serves as a significant income generator for agriculturalists in various cultivation zones (Akinyemi et al., 2010). In 2003, the ten leading banana-producing nations were responsible for nearly 75% of the global output, with India, Ecuador, Brazil, and China collectively making up almost half of that year's total production (Zhang et al., 2005).

However, bananas are notably perishable, leading to considerable financial losses, especially in countries like Pakistan, where the fruit's post-harvest lifespan is limited. Insects and other factors contribute to substantial global post-harvest losses in fruits and vegetables, sometimes reaching between 30 to 40%, with even higher percentages in certain developing countries. Minimizing these losses is imperative for ensuring global food security, reducing production costs, and enhancing the livelihood of farmers.

Bananas hold a special place in the diet of individuals residing in tropical regions, providing a wealth of essential nutrients such as fats, natural sugars, proteins, and vitamins like A, B-complex, and C. The fruit is not only easily digestible but also serves as a quick energy booster. Moreover, bananas have medicinal properties and can aid in conditions such as anemia, high blood pressure, and ulcers, among others. In developing countries, malnutrition and undernutrition pose significant challenges, impacting both economic and physical development. Reducing post-harvest losses can significantly improve per capita fruit availability, which is currently far below

the recommended daily intake. Various physiological and biochemical changes accompany the growth and development of the fruit (El-otmani et al., 1987). During the ripening process, starches are converted into simpler sugars, and the content of soluble pectin increases, resulting in fruit softening (Afshar et al., 2010). Effective storage technology can reduce post-harvest losses and extend the shelf life of this nutritious and economically valuable fruit.

The maturation of fruit is a complex process that involves notable shifts in elements like skin texture, juice quality, and flavor profile. The acidity level and mineral makeup can significantly affect enzyme activities in the cell wall, in turn influencing the stability of color pigments like anthocyanins (Huber and Donoghue, 1993). One key marker of fruit quality during the ripening process is the Total Soluble Solids (TSS), which is a measure of the fruit's sugar content (Lu, 2004). The ripening process also involves the breakdown of complex carbohydrates like starch into simpler sugars, and an increase in soluble pectins, which contributes to the fruit becoming softer (Afshar et al., 2010). Bananas, for example, can be harvested at varying developmental stages but can still attain high quality following ripening, particularly when ethylene gas is applied. Ethylene plays a critical role in facilitating changes such as color, texture, aroma, and flavor enhancement, while also influencing the overall ripening timeline. However, it's important to note that some aspects of the ripening can be isolated from the climacteric phase, which is the peak of the ripening process. In particular, the timing of color changes can differ among various fruits.

This study aims to explore the dynamics of banana ripening to aid in the design of new technologies for managing and extending the shelf life of fruits on a smaller scale. We assessed the impact of

variables like carbon dioxide and ethylene concentration, as well as temperature, on banana ripening. Samples were collected at intervals 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15 days for evaluations including weight loss, TSS levels, firmness, and ion interactions. The TSS content was determined using Abbe's refractometer by placing a drop of juice from the banana pulp onto the device's prism. The refractometer provided a direct reading of the TSS percentage. This increase in ethylene concentration is generally the pivotal factor for the ripening of fruits such as bananas, avocados, tomatoes, and melons (Bower et al., 2002).

This research endeavors to unravel the mechanisms involved in the ripening process of bananas with the ultimate goal of developing novel methods for fruit preservation and shelf-life extension. We conducted an in-depth analysis of factors such as carbon dioxide and ethylene levels, as well as ambient temperature, to understand their influence on banana maturation. Observations were made at specific time intervals 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15 days—focusing on changes in weight, total soluble solids (TSS), textural firmness, and ion exchange. TSS concentrations were measured using Abbe's refractometer, which offers direct percentage readings from a banana pulp juice sample (Ezez et al., 2023). It is well-established that a rise in ethylene levels plays a central role in the ripening of various fruits, including but not limited to, bananas, avocados, and melons.

Bananas are a rich source of essential nutrients like vitamin C, manganese, and potassium, each serving specific health benefits ranging from skin health to cardiovascular wellness (Ibrahim et al., 2023). According to the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) and the 2015–2020 Dietary Guidelines for Americans, a medium-sized banana can meet approximately 9% of daily potassium requirements for adults. Potassium is

crucial for blood pressure regulation and cardiovascular health (Jomova et al., 2022). Moreover, bananas have been proposed to have benefits in conditions such as asthma, owing to their antioxidant and potassium content. While some laboratory studies suggest that the lectin protein in bananas could inhibit the growth of leukemia cells, further research is needed.

Bananas also offer fiber, which is beneficial for heart health and blood sugar regulation. They are part of the BRAT diet, often recommended for diarrhea treatment, as they help in replenishing lost nutrients (Zou et al., 2022). However, for individuals with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), high-fiber foods like bananas could have varying effects and should be consumed cautiously. The study also aims to investigate physiological and biochemical changes in bananas at two distinct maturity stages during room temperature storage. This will provide further insights into how room temperature affects the storage and quality of bananas.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ripe fruits for the study were acquired from a local marketplace, whereas unripe specimens were sourced from an orchard in Uthal, Balochistan, on the day they were harvested. Selected bananas were uniform in shape, size, and maturity level, and devoid of any physical damage or signs of pest or pathogen infestation. Upon arrival at the Post-Harvest Laboratory of the Faculty of Agriculture at LUAWMS, the fruits underwent an initial rinse with water, a 15-minute immersion in a fungicidal solution, followed by a final rinse in sterilized water.

2.1. Instruments and reagents utilized

- Refractometer

- Penetrometer
- Conductivity Meter
- Precision Scale
- Distilled Water
- Water Bath

2.2. Quantification of fresh weight

To evaluate weight changes, three individual fruits from each experimental group were weighed using a precision scale at the outset of the study. These fruits were then periodically re-weighed throughout the storage duration. Weight loss serves as a critical indicator of post-harvest fruit quality, mainly due to the natural metabolic process of moisture evaporation leading to fruit deterioration. Weight loss was quantified via the formula:

Weight loss % = (Fruit initial weight – fruit weight at each sampling date) × 100/Fruit initial weight.

2.3. Evaluation of fruit firmness

The structural integrity of the fruit, an essential characteristic of fresh produce, was gauged using a digital penetrometer with an 8 mm probe. The force needed to insert the probe 5 mm into the fruit was measured and readings were taken at three equatorial points on each fruit.

2.4. Total soluble solids (TSS)

The juice from the fruits was extracted using an electric juicer. The Total Soluble Solids (TSS) were then quantified with a Digital Refractometer from Alla France. Soluble solids, mainly sugars, are a principal factor in assessing fruit quality. For this purpose, 10 grams of banana pulp was diluted in 40 ml of distilled water, homogenized, and filtered. The refractometer reading was then taken, with results recorded in % Brix.

2.5. Ion leakage

The cell membrane's integrity was assessed by slightly modifying the method proposed. Small cylinders were cut from four fruits in each batch using a 5 mm diameter cork borer. These were washed and placed in a glass vial containing 25 mL of deionized water, then agitated at 25°C for 30 minutes. Electrolyte leakage was evaluated using a conductivity meter (Radiometer Analytical Ion Check 65, France), before and after boiling the samples.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The study employed a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) for the experimental setup. The gathered data was rigorously analyzed using SAS software, with four replications and four treatments. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed to assess the data's overall significance, while the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test was used for pairwise comparison of treatment means.

3. RESULT

3.1. Extending shelf life and quality preservation

The study reveals significant implications for both retailers and consumers looking to prolong the freshness of bananas. By optimizing storage conditions at room temperature (25°C), the longevity of bananas can be extended by up to four days without compromising essential quality attributes such as sugar content and flavor. This approach mitigates the common issue of bruising that occurs during handling in supermarkets or within the home. Importantly, this elongation of shelf life can facilitate the entry of bananas into distant markets, as it minimizes post-harvest losses commonly attributed to suboptimal commercial practices.

3.2. Weight loss dynamics

During the storage period, both mature and immature bananas exhibited a progressive increase in weight loss. However, mature bananas were more susceptible, as illustrated in Figure 1. The least weight loss in mature bananas was registered at 9.3%,

whereas immature bananas displayed a minimum weight loss of 3.81% when stored at room temperature. This difference underscores the impact of maturity level on the respiration rate of the fruits, subsequently affecting their shelf life.

Figure:1 weight loss % of mature and immature banana.

3.3. Textural transformations

Figure 2 demonstrates the gradual textural changes occurring in all banana samples. The firmness of the bananas, a key indicator of ripeness, varied depending on the storage conditions and treatments applied. Initially, immature bananas exhibited a firmness of approximately 8.7 N, which was considerably less than the 13.5 N observed in mature bananas. However, after 12 days at 25°C, the firmness of mature bananas dropped to an average of 5 N, while immature bananas maintained a slightly higher firmness, ranging between 3.2 and 3.5 N.

3.4. Total soluble solids (TSS) trends

As demonstrated in Figure 3, the total soluble solids (TSS) in both mature and immature bananas progressively increased throughout the ripening process. The rate of this increase was influenced by the treatments and the storage duration. Mature

bananas averaged a TSS of 10°Brix, whereas the immature ones averaged 2°Brix. This small but statistically significant difference suggests that certain treatments can indeed delay the accumulation of sugars in bananas.

3.5. Cell membrane permeability

The permeability of the cell membrane in both mature and immature bananas escalated over the course of the storage period, as shown in Figure 4. Initially, mature bananas had a cell membrane permeability of 43.1%, which eventually rose to 85.7%. In contrast, the permeability in immature bananas ranged from 30% to 70%. This data implies that there was no decrease in cell membrane permeability in either group during the storage period.

The study provides a non-chemical method for extending the commercial life of bananas by up to four days, which is particularly beneficial for long-distance

shipping. Through carefully controlled room-temperature storage, the study also addresses key quality parameters like firmness, sugar content, and cell membrane permeability. Various instruments such as refractometers, penetrometers, and EC

meters were employed to quantify these parameters. By taking maturity levels into account, the study offers comprehensive insights into the post-harvest behavior of bananas.

Figure: 2 fruit firmness % of mature immature banana.

Figure: 3 TSS % of mature and immature banana.

Figure: 4 show ion leakage % of mature and immature banana.

4. DISCUSSION

Bananas are commonly harvested when they are fully matured but not yet ripe, displaying a firm texture and incomplete conversion of starch to sugars (Hsu et al., 2023). After the harvest, they are often stored at specific room temperatures and may be treated with ethylene. Ethylene is renowned for its capability to prolong freshness, delay the ripening process, and extend the shelf-life of not only bananas but also a wide array of fruits, vegetables, and ornamental plants (Mariah et al., 2022). When bananas are stored at room temperature and exposed to ethylene, research has shown that the natural increase in ethylene production and the consequent softening of the fruit can be delayed, thus extending its shelf life to up to 30 days when stored at 13°C (Ali et al., 2022). Various facets of ripening such as softening, color change, and sugar content, align closely with the pattern of ethylene production (Brown & Summers, 2017). Assessing the maturity of freshly harvested bananas is an essential factor affecting their market appeal and overall quality (Belay 2022). A recent study delved into a non-intrusive, image-processing technique employing a mean color intensity algorithm to predict the fruit's maturity (Kharbach et al., 2023). The algorithm demonstrated an

impressive average classification accuracy rate of approximately 99.1%. This technological advancement could revolutionize how bananas are harvested by ensuring they are picked at the optimal stage of maturity, thus maximizing economic returns for producers (Luangchosiri, 2023).

Moreover, cellular energy has a significant role in controlling the ripening and senescence of post-harvest horticultural products (Wang et al., 2013). Studies indicate that in fruits sensitive to low temperatures, chilling injuries and physiological disorders might be associated with a drop in cellular energy levels (Liu et al., 2011; Zou et al., 2022). This energy shortfall could directly affect the biosynthesis of membrane lipids and cell membrane restoration, thereby modulating the fruit's resilience to cold-induced stress (Jin et al., 2014). In summary, careful management of factors such as storage temperature, ethylene treatment, and cellular energy levels can have a significant influence on the ripening, quality, and shelf life of bananas. Innovations like image-based maturity prediction can offer further optimization, potentially transforming the

economics of banana production (McLennon et al., 2021).

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Funding: This research has not been funded by any institute.

Authors' contributions: This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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